

Farm2Export: Ammonia

A Farm2Export report funded by DAERA's SBRI and developed in collaboration with the UKCEH.

An assessment of ammonia emissions across the Farm2Export supply chain, from slurry separation to bio-based fertiliser, and its role in transitioning to a circular nutrient economy.

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Disclaimer

This report was prepared by BH Estates in collaboration with the UK Centre for Ecology and Hydrology (UKCEH). This report has been prepared as a scientifically independent process. The views and conclusions expressed are those of the authors and do not necessarily reflect policies of the contributing organisations. This work is an expert contribution to the Farm2Export project.

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Farm2Export: Ammonia

An assessment of ammonia emissions across the Farm2Export supply chain, from slurry separation to bio-based fertiliser, and its role in transitioning to a circular nutrient economy.

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INMS

≈ uPcycle

List of Abbreviations

Acronym	Description
AD	Anaerobic Digestion
ASSI	Area of Special Scientific Interest (<i>Northern Ireland designation</i>)
BBF	Bio-based Fertiliser
BHE	Blakiston Houston Estates
CHP	Combined Heat and Power
DAERA	Department of Agriculture, Environment and Rural Affairs (<i>Northern Ireland</i>)
EF	Emission Factor
F2E	Farm to Export
INMS	The 'towards an International Nitrogen Management System' project
LESSE	Low Emission Slurry Spreading Equipment
NH ₃	Ammonia
(NH ₄) ₂ SO ₄	Ammonium Sulphate
SAC	Special Area of Conservation
SBRI	Small Business Research Initiative
SPA	Special Protection Area
SULS	Sustainable Utilisation of Livestock Slurry
TAN	Total Ammoniacal Nitrogen
UKCEH	UK Centre for Ecology & Hydrology
uPcycle	The 'Towards Sustainable Phosphorus Cycles in Lake Catchments' project

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Executive summary

Overview

The Farm2Export project, launched in 2023 under the Sustainable Utilisation of Livestock Slurry programme and partly funded by the Department of Agriculture, Environment and Rural Affairs (DAERA), is developing an integrated nutrient recovery system for Northern Ireland.

This system combines on-farm slurry management with processing at anaerobic digestion plants to recover and redistribute nutrients efficiently. At the farm, a mobile screw press is used to separate slurry into a liquid fraction, which remains on site and supports the use of Low Emission Slurry Spreading Equipment (LESSE), and a dryer, solid fraction, which is transported to anaerobic digestion facilities. After anaerobic digestion, the resulting digestate is further separated and dried to remove additional liquid. This secondary liquid can also be applied locally as a nutrient source, while the dried solid digestate is processed into a bio-based fertiliser with concentrated stabilised nutrients that can be easily exported from nutrient-rich areas.

The purpose of this report is to:

- Model the Farm2Export process by tracking material flows through the nutrient supply chain, to determine the scale of biomass recovery required to supply one bio-based fertiliser plant.
- Quantify ammonia emissions across the entire supply chain relative to conventional manure and digestate management practices.
- Discuss the potential challenges and opportunities associated with the deployment of the Farm2Export nutrient recovery supply chain.

This report is intended to be useful for policymakers, regulators, researchers and stakeholders in agriculture and environmental management, providing evidence and guidance on nutrient recovery and sustainable manure management.

Key findings

Developing manure treatment processes that separate, stabilise and convert slurry into transportable bio-based fertilisers offers an opportunity to rebalance regional nutrient cycles, alleviate nutrient loading pressures, reduce environmental impacts and enhance farm viability.

The following criteria were used to model the Farm2Export supply chain for a single bio-based fertiliser plant:

- *Farm level:* Around 1,430 farms, each with 100 dairy cows, supply slurry solids.
- *Anaerobic digestion plants:* 21 plants, each with 500-kW combined heat and power units, digest the slurry solids into digestate and then supply digestate solids.
- *Dryers:* Seven dryers remove additional moisture from the digestate solids, producing feedstock for a single bio-based fertiliser plant.

Modelling the Farm2Export supply chain shows this process can achieve **an 11% reduction in ammonia emissions compared with conventional manure and digestate management**. This assumes Low Emission Slurry Spreading Equipment (LESSE) is used on an additional quarter of farms and slurry solids constitute 75% of anaerobic digestion feedstock.

This ammonia saving equates to a **12% contribution to meeting Northern Ireland's agricultural ammonia reduction target**, relative to 2005 levels, to be achieved by 2030. This represents a significant contribution to addressing the region's ammonia challenge.

The Farm2Export supply chain also reduces phosphorus losses by removing nutrient-rich slurry solids from critical source areas. Preliminary results indicate that **a single bio-based fertiliser plant could decrease the national phosphorus surplus by 7%**, via redistribution of phosphorus to nutrient-deficient regions. This assumes a national phosphorus surplus of approximately 7,000 tonnes.

This approach improves farm-level nutrient efficiency, partly through increased use of Low Emission Slurry Spreading Equipment (LESSE). It also supports renewable energy production via anaerobic digestion plants and creates jobs in nutrient processing, transport and bio-based fertiliser production.

While the Farm2Export supply chain offers significant opportunities, adherence to the Interim and Proposed Operational Protocol for evaluating ammonia impacts on designated sites could limit the wider adoption of manure processing technologies. This is largely due to how spatial interactions and trade-offs are interpreted. We highlight the need to redefine potential trade-offs and identify synergies to maximise environmental net gain.

Recommendations

1. Encourage slurry separation and maximise use of slurry solids in anaerobic digestion plants.

- *Liquid fraction:* Keep on the farm, where its liquid form allows easy handling and application using Low Emission Slurry Spreading Equipment (LESSE). Improved soil infiltration reduces ammonia losses and enhances nutrient uptake.
- *Solid fraction:* Process through anaerobic digestion plants to concentrate nutrients into a transportable form. This allows export of nutrients from surplus areas to nutrient-deficient regions, supporting more balanced regional nutrient cycles. Anaerobic digestion of solids generates biogas for renewable energy.

2. Optimise digestate management.

- Further separation and drying of digestate reduces ammonia emissions at anaerobic digestion plants and produces feedstock for bio-based fertiliser.
- Apply digestate liquids locally can maintain nutrient use efficiency and reduce ammonia losses.

3. Align nitrogen and phosphorus governance.

- Align nitrogen and phosphorus policies to work in a coordinated way to enhance the efficient use of nutrients, reduce environmental risk and create more predictable outcomes for farms and investors.

4. Review planning frameworks.

- Explore opportunities to ensure manure separation and nutrient recovery technologies can be deployed under planning regulations while remaining compliant with legal requirements such as the Habitats Directive.
- Use insights from this study to update guidance and planning processes, formalising the impact of manure separation on ammonia emissions to create a clear pathway for sustainable deployment of technologies.

5. Support nutrient recovery technologies.

- Enable wider adoption of nutrient recovery technologies through incentives, policy tools and regulatory support. Evidence shows these technologies reduce ammonia emissions, limit environmental damage and lower investment risk for farms and operators.

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Photo: The atmosphere is mostly nitrogen (around 78%), but reactive nitrogen compounds released from agriculture, industry and energy use can travel far and impact air, water, and ecosystems. Effective nutrient management helps minimise these losses while supporting sustainable food production.

Introduction

1.1 The global nitrogen and phosphorus challenge

Nitrogen and phosphorus are essential nutrients for plants, playing a critical role in agriculture. However, their widespread mismanagement has become a leading cause of economic loss and environmental degradation, threatening air and water quality, biodiversity and climate stability (Sutton et al., 2021; Brownlie et al., 2022b). Alarmingly, both nutrients have now exceeded their planetary boundaries, which are critical thresholds beyond which Earth's systems face the risk of instability (Rockström et al., 2009; Richardson et al., 2023). Addressing these challenges demands coordinated, timely action from local to global levels.

The 'nitrogen challenge', as described by Sutton et al., (2021), lies in the need to balance nitrogen's vital role in food security with its environmental consequences. Reactive nitrogen compounds, including ammonia (NH_3), nitrate (NO_3^-), nitrous oxide (N_2O) and nitrogen oxides (NO_x), are released into the air, soils and water from a variety of sources, particularly agriculture, but also through fossil fuel combustion and industrial processes (Sutton et al., 2022). These emissions contribute to multiple environmental impacts, including smog formation, acidification, eutrophication, biodiversity loss and greenhouse gas emissions. Despite growing international recognition, through the United Nations Environment Assembly resolutions and declarations calling for integrated nitrogen management (UNEP, 2019b, 2019a, 2022), policies remain siloed and fragmented from national to global levels, limiting progress toward coherent and effective solutions (Morseletto, 2019; Sutton et al., 2021).

Phosphorus, although not recognised as a major atmospheric pollutant, follows a similarly problematic trajectory when mismanaged (Brownlie et al., 2021). Phosphorus losses from farms, urban runoff and wastewater discharge can accumulate in water bodies, especially lakes, triggering long-term water quality deterioration through toxic algal blooms (Johnes et al., 2022; Masso et al., 2022). These blooms impair ecosystems, release methane (a potent greenhouse gas), threaten fisheries and drinking water supplies and are intensified by climate change (Beaulieu et al., 2019; WWQA Ecosystems, 2023). In this context, nutrient pollution has broad implications for public health, economic vitality, national security and environmental sustainability.

Despite their differences, the management of nitrogen and phosphorus is deeply interlinked (Kanter and Brownlie, 2019). Both are mobilised through fertilisers (synthetic and organic), including manure and other organic wastes. Both suffer from inefficiencies in use and from spatial imbalances; too much in some landscapes and too little in others. Both offer enormous opportunities for recovery and reuse through circular economy principles (Sutton et al., 2013; Hermann et al., 2022). Instead of viewing nitrogen and phosphorus losses as purely environmental liabilities, they should be seen as untapped resources: *pollution that can be transformed into part of the solution, to allow reduced inputs of newly accessed nitrogen and phosphorus resources.*

This perspective is especially relevant for Northern Ireland, where nutrient balances exceed crop demand, increasing the risk of nutrient loss to water bodies and the atmosphere (Rothwell et al., 2020; Carnell et al., 2021). However, with smarter, more-integrated management, excess nutrients can be transformed from a source of pollution into a valuable resource with potential for reuse and export, promoting development of the circular bioeconomy (Brownlie et al., 2024a). This also supports national security by reducing food security risks associated with volatile fertiliser markets (Brownlie et al., 2022b)

1.2 Principles of integrated sustainable nutrient management

Nutrient management has often been tackled through sector- or nutrient-specific strategies, focusing on nitrogen or phosphorus in isolation and targeting individual sources or impacts solutions (Cordell and Neset, 2014; Morseletto, 2019). This fragmented approach falls short of addressing the complex, interconnected dynamics of nutrient flows in agricultural landscapes and aquatic ecosystems. Nitrogen and phosphorus cycles overlap and interact with multiple environmental, social and economic factors across various spatial and temporal scales, jointly driving water quality issues like eutrophication, and contributing to biodiversity loss, soil degradation, impaired ecosystem functioning and greenhouse gas emissions (Brownlie et al., 2024).

To effectively protect water resources, sustain agricultural productivity, and preserve ecosystem health, nutrient management must be integrated across nutrients, sources, sectors and scales

(Oenema et al., 2011; Sarvajayakesavalu et al., 2018). This integrated approach ensures coordinated action that considers the full nutrient cycle, reduces unintended trade-offs and promotes sustainable, circular nutrient use.

Based on existing research and best practices (Sutton et al., 2022; Brownlie et al., 2024), we present a list of principles that should be considered when developing integrated nutrient management strategies. Below is a summary of the key principles that guide effective and sustainable nutrient management, with further details on each principle provided in the [Appendix](#):

Key principles of integrated nutrient management:

1. Address all sources, forms and movement of nutrients across space and time.
2. Reducing nutrient inputs is essential for controlling pollution.
3. Reductions in nutrient losses must be matched by decreases in inputs or increases in outputs.
4. Managing internal nutrient loading (e.g. from soils and lake sediments) is critical for aquatic ecosystem restoration.
5. Transitioning to circular nutrient systems enhances sustainability.
6. Co-managing nitrogen and phosphorus maximises efficiency and benefits.
7. Site-specific management based on local conditions is essential.
8. Cost-effective solutions and stakeholder involvement are critical for success.
9. Shared responsibility across multiple sectors is necessary.
10. Trade-offs must be considered when setting priorities.

1.3 Regional nutrient imbalances in Northern Ireland

Northern Ireland's nutrient management challenges mirror global agricultural issues but are intensified by local factors. The region's livestock-dominated farming system, combined with a physical separation between livestock and arable farms, results in uneven nutrient distribution. This leads to localised nitrogen and phosphorus surpluses, particularly affecting sensitive water bodies such as Lough Neagh (Cassidy et al., 2019; Rothwell et al., 2020). High fertiliser and feed inputs disrupt natural nutrient cycles, increasing nutrient runoff risks that degrade water quality and prevent compliance with EU Water Framework Directive targets.

Recent harmful algal blooms of 2023, 2024 and 2025 occurred in Lough Neagh, the UK and Ireland's largest freshwater lake. These were driven by excess phosphorus and nitrogen from runoff and legacy sediments, exacerbated by extreme weather and climate change (Rippey et al., 2022; Reid et al., 2024). In response, the Department of Agriculture, Environment and Rural Affairs (DAERA) launched the Lough Neagh Report and Action Plan in July 2024 (DAERA, 2024a), focusing on education, regulation, investment and improved manure management, including farmer training and technological innovation to optimise nutrient reuse and reduce losses. Other water bodies in Northern Ireland have either experienced, or are at risk of eutrophication.

Ammonia emissions, predominantly from agriculture (97%), present a parallel concern. Though Northern Ireland covers only 6% of the UK's land area, it accounts for approximately 12% of UK ammonia emissions (~30.9 kt in 2022) (DAERA, 2024b). Northern Ireland contains 394 protected sites recognised for their high nature conservation value, of which 250 are sensitive to the effects of ammonia and atmospheric nitrogen. Most of these designated sites are currently subject to ammonia concentrations and nitrogen deposition rates that exceed the critical levels and loads, leading to expected adverse effects on plants and biodiversity (DAERA, 2023). It is estimated that 100% of Special Areas of Conservation (SACs), 100% of Special Protection Areas (SPAs) and 99.7% of Areas of Special Scientific Interest (ASSIs) in Northern Ireland have ammonia concentrations greater than $1 \mu\text{g m}^{-3}$ (the long-term annual average critical level for lichens and mosses, and for ecosystems in which they are important) (DAERA, 2023). This illustrates the challenge of air pollution and habitat deterioration from ammonia in Northern Ireland.

1.4 Nutrient recovery and circular bioeconomy solutions

Addressing agricultural nutrient imbalances and subsequent pollution, while at the same time supporting a circular bioeconomy, requires recovery and redistribution of nutrients from livestock manure and organic residues. Separation technologies enable slurry to be partitioned into solid and liquid fractions. This then allows more targeted nutrient management. For example, phosphorus-rich solids (with a 60% higher phosphorus concentration than raw slurry) can be transported to nutrient-deficient areas or processed further. Similarly, nitrogen-rich liquids (containing >70% of the total nitrogen) can be applied locally, enabling easier use of Low Emission Slurry Spreading Equipment (LESSE) such as trailing hose, trailing shoe or injection applications to reduce ammonia volatilisation (Brownlie et al., 2022a, 2024). LESSE refers to machinery designed to apply livestock slurry or equivalent to land in a way that reduces ammonia emissions, odour, and nutrient loss compared with traditional splash plate spreading. An effective way to increase the amount of nutrient available for crop growth from slurry application, while reducing loss of nutrients.

The solid fraction can also serve as feedstock for anaerobic digestion (AD), producing renewable biogas to displace fossil fuels and yielding digestate. The digestate can be separated

into solid and liquid fractions, which can then be processed into a bio-based fertiliser (BBF) (Mehta et al., 2022). Such BBFs can facilitate nutrient redistribution beyond nutrient-rich catchments or countries, helping rebalance nitrogen and phosphorus cycles while supporting renewable energy and greenhouse gas mitigation.

The Lough Neagh Report and Action Plan highlight the need for improved manure management to reduce nutrient pollution (DAERA, 2024a). Its “Incentivisation/Innovation” pillar supports scaling slurry processing technologies, aiming to reduce excessive land-spreading of nutrients.

Within this context, improved manure management is necessary and offers a critical opportunity to reduce both air and water pollution. Proper storage and handling of organic residues can minimise ammonia losses to air and phosphorus losses to water, thus reducing nutrient pollution and its impacts. Similarly, nutrient stabilisation and conversion into BBFs can facilitate transport to nutrient-deficient areas, promoting circular nutrient reuse while reducing local surpluses. However, implementing manure processing at the individual farm level can present significant economic and logistical challenges. This highlights the potential benefits of a centralised manure handling and processing system that can improve the economic performance of the concept.

The Farm2Export (F2E) project, managed by Blakiston Houston Estates (BHE), launched under the Sustainable Utilisation of Livestock Slurry (SULS) programme in 2023 and part-funded by DAERA through the Small Business Research Initiative (SBRI), aims to support the development of such a circular bioeconomy solution. Developing manure treatment processes that separate, stabilise and convert slurry into transportable BBFs can help rebalance regional nutrient cycles, reduce environmental impacts and support farm viability. The Lough Neagh Report and Action Plan already prioritise scaling slurry processing technologies through initiatives like the SULS programme, illustrating a clear path forward (DAERA, 2024a).

1.5 Planning and the deployment of nutrient recovery

Planning legislation plays an important role in protecting designated sites from ammonia emissions. Its requirements and assessment methods can, however, present complexities when dealing with manure processing technologies. Air quality impact assessments need to consider ammonia sources and effects on protected sites, while the wider emission reduction potential from the development can sometimes be difficult to express.

Currently in Northern Ireland, a ‘Revised Operational Protocol for assessing ammonia and air pollution impacts on the natural environment’ (Operational Protocol) exists for assessing ammonia and air pollution impacts on the natural environment (i.e., when seeking planning permission for ‘plans or projects’) (DAERA, 2025a). The Operational Protocol focuses on procedures for the assessment of planning applications related to ammonia emissions from

livestock facilities, including manure processing. The guidance uses screening thresholds to assess the likelihood of adverse effects arising from a proposed plan or project, which in turn determines its eligibility for planning permission. The guidance aims to assist applicants and decision-makers in assessing whether agricultural developments would impact sites protected under the Conservation (Natural Habitats, etc.) Regulations (Northern Ireland) 1995 or the Environment (Northern Ireland) Order 2002.

The requirements within the Operational Protocol for ammonia impact assessment can impact the deployment of manure processing technologies in Northern Ireland. New or replacement developments (including technology) within 7.5 km of designated sites (zones of influence) require air quality impact assessments. There are around 500 designated sites in Northern Ireland (OEP, 2025), with different classifications of sites including Special Areas of Conservation (SACs), Special Protection Areas (SPAs) and Areas of Special Scientific Interest (ASSIs), almost all of which exceed critical levels for ammonia (Section 1.3 & **Figure 1**). The large number of SACs, SPAs and ASSIs, and the substantial screening distance, mean that assessments often need to consider multiple sensitive sites and interacting sources, which can often limit planning approval.

The assessment procedure takes into account a 'critical level' and a 'critical load' for each designated site. The critical level refers to the concentration of pollutants in the atmosphere ($\mu\text{g m}^{-3}$), above which direct adverse effects on receptors such as plants and ecosystems may occur. The critical load is defined as the exposure, in the form of deposition ($\text{kg N ha}^{-1} \text{ yr}^{-1}$), of one or more pollutants, below which direct and indirect effects do not occur. These definitions apply 'according to current knowledge' (DAERA, 2025a). A 'process contribution' is then calculated by comparing pollutant concentration or deposition from the new development against the relevant critical level or critical level/load, respectively, for the site in question at relevant distances and directions from the source. Depending on the process contribution, the impact will fall between different ammonia thresholds, which will direct how the plan or project is assessed further and the significance of impact (DAERA, 2025a):

1. De-minimus Threshold (DMT): If the process contribution is under the DMT threshold (0.08% of critical level for ammonia) no further assessment is required, and the effects are recognised as insignificant alone.
2. When the DMT is deemed too conservative, Site Relevant Thresholds (SRT) are applied: SRTs range from 0.08 - 0.75% of the critical level for ammonia. If the process contribution falls within this range, no further assessment is required and the effects are recognised as insignificant alone.
3. When the process contribution is above the DMT and SRT, the screening threshold and an in-combination assessment is applied. The process contribution is evaluated alongside other plans or projects, and if the in-combination contribution is under the screening threshold of 1% of the critical level for ammonia, no further assessment is needed. If the in-combination contribution is above the screening threshold of 1%, a detailed assessment must be undertaken.

If the nitrogen or ammonia deposition impact of the project or plan surpasses the third screening threshold, a detailed assessment considers other components including background levels, mitigation and spatially targeted measures. If this threshold is surpassed without adequate mitigation, the protocol considers that there would be air quality concerns and the development would be deemed ineligible for planning permission (DAERA, 2025a).

The extensive spatial distribution of zones of influence i.e., the initial screening distance used to assess if there are sensitive sites that could be affected (DAERA, 2025a), is presented in **Figure 1**. A screening distance of 7.5km from designated sites was used for the creation of this map, reflecting the assessment distance for the majority of agricultural developments. With a high distribution of sensitive designated sites with low critical loads/levels for nitrogen or ammonia deposition, the process contribution (impact) of prospective new developments is often relatively high and non-compliant.

While large-scale or widespread nutrient recovery systems show potential for redistributing and rebalancing agricultural nutrients, the planning framework to assess technologies that process materials containing reactive nitrogen, including manures, slurries and AD digestates, can limit planning approval.

Figure 1. Designated network of ecological sites in Northern Ireland with 7.5 km screening zones around each site. Screening zones indicate the area within which proposed plans and projects should be assessed in their impact on designated sites.

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Photo: Dairy cattle produce manure that, when managed effectively, can become a valuable nutrient resource. Proper handling and storage help minimise environmental impacts while supporting sustainable nutrient recycling on farms.

The Farm2Export project: A case study in nutrient circularity

2.1 The Farm2Export project

Launched under the Sustainable Utilisation of Livestock Slurry (SULS) programme in 2023, the Farm2Export project (F2E) strives to demonstrate integrated nutrient recovery in Northern Ireland. The F2E aims to establish a nutrient supply chain by recovering nutrients from farms and anaerobic digestion (AD) sites and processing them into commercially viable bio-based fertiliser (BBF).

The project involves:

1. Nutrient recovery at farm scale via mechanical separation of slurry (**Figure 2**), creating slurry solids for biogas production for AD plants, and liquid slurry to stay on the farm site, with lower dry matter than raw slurry, allowing easier infiltration and easier adoption of Low Emission Slurry Spreading Equipment (LESSE).
2. Nutrient recovery at AD plants via mechanical separation of AD digestate, creating digestate solids for a further drying step, and liquid digestate to stay at the AD site, with lower dry matter than raw digestate, allowing easier infiltration when applied.
3. Solid digestate drying of the digestate to significantly reduce moisture, weight and volume, concentrating nutrients for efficient transport and further treatment.
4. Production of BBF from processed digestate for sustainable nutrient redistribution.

Figure 2. (a) A mobile screw press on a trailer, delivered by tractor, processing cattle slurry (a mixture of manure, urine, water and organic matter). The slurry is pumped into an auger (corkscrew), where it is compressed to separate fractions. Liquid is forced through a perforated screen and collected via a pipe for on-farm storage, while the solid fraction is expelled from the outlet chute and piled for transport off-farm as anaerobic digestion feedstock. (b) Close-up of the auger showing slurry entering the press and the start of the separation process.

This approach reduces nutrient loading on sensitive environments, by redistributing agricultural nutrients and supports energy sector de-carbonisation through renewable biogas production.

Initial modelling and implementation highlight the potential of the F2E to reduce nutrient loading and foster a circular bioeconomy for nutrients in Northern Ireland. However, formal quantification of nitrogen flows and ammonia emissions across the system remains necessary. To address this, BH Estates and the UK Centre for Ecology & Hydrology (UKCEH) collaborated on mass balance modelling of biomass flows and ammonia losses throughout the supply chain. This report presents our findings, offering critical insights into associated ammonia emission reductions relative to conventional manure and digestate management.

2.2 Aims and objectives of this study

The aim of this study is to evaluate the impact of the F2E nutrient recovery supply chain on ammonia emissions at a whole system scale, while considering both the potential opportunities and challenges associated with the deployment of the supply chain.

To achieve this aim, the study has the following objectives:

1. **Model the F2E material supply chain** by tracking biomass¹ flows to determine the scale of nutrient recovery required to supply one BBF plant.
2. **Quantify ammonia emissions across the entire F2E supply chain**, comparing ammonia emissions to those from conventional manure and digestate management practices.
3. **Discuss potential co-benefits associated with the F2E supply chain** including reductions in nutrient loading and nutrient loss, and improvements in water and air quality, as well as the implications of the current regulatory approach to ammonia assessments on the ability to take advantage of these opportunities in Northern Ireland.

¹ Biomass in this context refers to slurry, slurry solids, slurry liquids, anaerobic digester feedstock, digestate, digestate solids, digestate liquids, dry digestate.

Photo: A pile of solid material discharged from the outlet of a mobile screw press on a farm. The screw press separates slurry into liquid and solid fractions, making the solid portion easier to handle, store, and transport off-farm, whilst the liquid fraction remains on-farm for use with low emission slurry spreading equipment.

Methodology: assessing ammonia emissions in the Farm2Export supply chain

3.1 Modelling the Farm2Export supply chain

The Farm2Export project (F2E) supply chain is divided into four process stages to track biomass flows and simplify modelling of ammonia emissions. Each stage corresponds to a location where material is handled, stored or processed.

The stages, as shown in **Figure 3**, are:

1. Livestock farm,
2. Anaerobic digestion (AD) facilities,
3. Dryer facilities and
4. Bio-based fertiliser (BBF) plant.

Figure 3. The four stages of the F2E supply chain, with descriptions.

1. Livestock farm

Slurry is separated on-site using a screw-press separator, removing solids and leaving the liquid fraction on the farm for land spreading. This reduces the need to transport high-moisture material and concentrates nutrients in the separated solids for further processing in external facilities/ outside the farm.

2. Anaerobic digester plant

The separated solids are processed in a digester to generate biogas, with the resulting digestate separated using a decanting centrifuge. This produces digestate solids and liquid that can be managed or treated separately. Liquid digestate is used locally as fertiliser and solids are further processed, improving nutrient recovery efficiency.

3. Dryer facilities

The separated digestate solids undergo thermal drying to reduce moisture content, improve product stability, reduce weight and volume for transport, and lower the risk of odour and microbial activity during storage. The facilities include an ammonia scrubber which captures most of the ammonia released by the drying process.

4. Bio-based fertiliser plant

The dried digestate solids are converted into a nutrient-stable, market-ready fertiliser product. Processes are designed to optimise nutrient availability while minimising losses and can integrate carbon capture technologies to embed carbon within the product, supporting greenhouse gas and ammonia reduction alongside nutrient recycling.

3.2 Assumptions for calculating material flows through the F2E supply chain

The F2E supply chain model was developed by estimating biomass flows at each process stage, working backwards from one BBF plant to determine the required material quantities and processing steps. The output from each process stage serves as the input for the next stage. To track solid material flows through the system, the following key assumptions were made. Further assumptions relating to ammonia emissions are detailed in Section 3.3.

Livestock Farm

- Since the farm's organic material comes from animal excretion, there is no external input flow; the main biomass output is slurry solids.
- One 'standard' farm is estimated to export circa 154 tonnes of slurry solids each year, assuming: a standard farm size of 100 milking cows, 0.37 m³ of slurry produced each week and animals housed all year round. Separation using a mobile screw-press (Figure 2), which is commercially available equipment, is carried out on each farm. Using this equipment ~8% of the total slurry weight can be partitioned into the solid fraction and exported from the farm to an AD plant.

Anaerobic digester plant

- One AD plant is assumed to process 13,000–15,000 tonnes of biomass feedstock per year, depending on the proportion of slurry solids used. Of the total feedstock, 50–100% is assumed to come from slurry solids generated by on-farm separation, while 0–50% is grass silage. Supplying this quantity of slurry solids would require 42–97 feeder farms. Because slurry solids have a lower energy content than grass silage, higher proportions of slurry solids correspond to higher total annual feedstock tonnage.
- An estimated 10% of the feedstock mass is assumed to be converted to biogas during digestion. This reflects typical 500 kW agriculturally-fed AD plants in Northern Ireland.
- The AD process produces digestate (estimated at 90% of the total feedstock mass), which is separated into a solid and liquid fraction using a decanting centrifuge. For this process, the raw digestate and digestate solids are assumed to be 7% and 27% dry matter content respectively, and the separation efficiency for total solids is 65%. The liquid fraction of the digestate is assumed to have a dry matter content of 5%.
- The digestate solids (created from the separation step) are exported from the AD plant, representing the biomass import to the drying step. Between 1,972 and 2,275 tonnes of solid digestate are assumed to be exported from each AD annually, depending on the feedstock proportion used (illustrated in **Table 1**).
- The liquid digestate fraction is spread on a farm/farms in the vicinity of the AD plant.

Table 1. Material flows (tonnes⁻¹ yr⁻¹) through the anaerobic digester (AD) plant as affected by the proportion of slurry solids in the feedstock.

Feedstock proportion, % slurry solids*	Total feedstock per plant tonnes ⁻¹ yr ⁻¹	Farms providing slurry solids i.e., feeder farms	Output (digestate solids) tonnes ⁻¹ yr ⁻¹ AD plant ⁻¹
50%	13,000	42	1,972
75%	14,000	68	2,123
100%	15,000	97	2,275

*Remaining feedstock assumed to be grass silage

Dryer facilities

- It is assumed that one dryer is fed 6,500 tonnes of digestate solids each year at 27% dry matter. One dryer is fed by 3 AD plants. The capacity of dryer is around 600 kW and was set at this size using waste heat assessments from a 500 kW combined heat and power AD plant.
- The dry digestate output from the dryer is assumed to be 80% dry matter, reducing the mass of the input digestate solids from 6,500 to 2,200 tonnes due to water removal.

Bio-based fertiliser plant

- One BBF plant is assumed to be fed 15,000 tonnes of dried solid digestate annually at 80% dry matter. The dry digestate input is produced by 7 dryers and represents 50% of the total output flow i.e., 30,000 tonnes of output BBF. This size of plant is representative of a plant currently under planning consultation within the F2E project

Table 2 summarises the input/output biomass flows for each process stage, and the quantity of processes that make up the whole F2E supply chain.

Table 2. Material flows through the four principal stages of the F2E supply chain: livestock farm, anaerobic digester (AD) plant, dryer facilities and bio-based fertiliser (BBF) plant. Tonnage values expressed as fresh mass. ‘Supply chain’ refers to the process stages required to supply one BBF plant.

1. Livestock farm			
Biomass input/farm (tonnes yr ⁻¹)	N/A		
Biomass output/farm (tonnes yr ⁻¹)	154		
Total feeder farms for 1 AD plant (no. of farms)**	47	68	97
Total quantity in supply chain (no. of farms)**	950	1,430	1,900
2. Anaerobic digester (AD) plant			
Biomass input/AD (tonnes yr ⁻¹)**	13,000	14,000	15,000
Proportion of slurry solids as feedstock (%)**	50	75	100
Biomass output/AD (tonnes yr ⁻¹)**	1,972	2,123	2,275
Total quantity in supply chain (No. of AD plants)**	23	21	20
Total feeder AD plants for 1 dryer (No. of AD plants)	3		
3. Dryer facilities			
Biomass input/dryer (tonnes yr ⁻¹)	6,500		
Biomass input/dryer (tonnes yr ⁻¹)	2,200		
Total quantity in supply chain (No. of dryers)	7		
3. Bio-based fertiliser (BBF) plant			
Biomass input/BBF plant (tonnes yr ⁻¹)	15,000		
Biomass input/BBF plant (tonnes yr ⁻¹)	30,000		
Total quantity in supply chain (No. of BBF plants)	1		

*No ‘input’ of biomass to the farm due to manure production

**Range representing different proportion of slurry solids used as AD feedstock (50–100%).

3.3 Assumptions for calculating ammonia emissions from the F2E supply chain

For this analysis, ammonia emissions were calculated across the full F2E supply chain. The first three principal stages: 1. Livestock farm, 2. AD plant and 3. Dryer facilities, were identified as ammonia emission sources. The final stage, 4. BBF plant, was not considered a significant source of ammonia emissions in the context of this study due to the low water content of the input dry digestate material (<20%).

Ammonia emissions from the livestock farm and AD facilities were calculated as the difference between emissions under a conventional baseline and those generated within the F2E supply chain system. The conventional baseline assumes no separation or movement of slurry solids or solid digestate away from farms or AD sites, while the F2E supply chain assumes separation at both farm and AD sites, along with export of the solid fraction.

Emissions from the dryer facilities were assumed to be new under the F2E supply chain and therefore, no comparison with a conventional baseline was made. Ammonia emission sources within the F2E supply chain are summarised in **Table 3**, and **Figure 4** illustrates the conventional baseline farm versus the farm operating within the F2E supply chain.

Table 3 Ammonia emission sources under a conventional baseline and within the F2E supply chain

Stages	Ammonia emissions sources	
	Conventional baseline	F2E supply chain
1. Livestock farm	Livestock housing	Livestock housing
	Slurry storage (raw slurry)	Slurry storage (raw and liquid slurry fraction)
	Slurry application to land (raw slurry)	Slurry application to land (liquid slurry fraction)
2. Anaerobic digester plant	Feedstock storage (excluding slurry solids)	Feedstock storage (including slurry solids)
	Digestate storage (raw digestate)	Digestate storage (raw and liquid digestate)
	Digestate application to land (raw digestate)	Digestate application to land (liquid digestate fraction)
3. Dryer facilities	N/A	Biomass storage
		Drying process

Figure 4. Conventional Northern Irish cattle farm system (top) and a farm within the F2E supply chain (bottom), showing the four principal process stages: livestock farm, anaerobic digester (AD) plant, dryer facilities and bio-based fertiliser (BBF) plant.

Conventional Northern Irish cattle farm system

Alternative F2E farm system

3.3.1 Assumptions for livestock farms in the F2E supply chain

For the livestock farm stage, ammonia emissions were estimated from animal housing, as well as the storage and application of slurry/liquid slurry material. To quantify the ammonia emissions from a livestock farm within the F2E system, the following assumptions were made.

- Mechanical separation of slurry using screw-press technology was carried out on each farm (**Figure 1**). This process produced a solid slurry fraction that was exported (with no associated on-farm emissions) and a liquid slurry fraction that was stored before being applied to land, replacing the spreading of raw unprocessed slurry.
- The separated liquid slurry fraction has a lower dry matter content than the original raw slurry (from 7% to 5%) therefore displacing raw slurry with a separated slurry liquid fraction for land spreading reduced ammonia emission in two main ways:
 1. through an increase in infiltration, and
 2. a switch from conventional broadcast splash plate application to bandspreading, via trailing hose. As pipes of a trailing hose become clogged if the dry matter content of the slurry is high (>7%) or if the slurry contains large particles (Oenema et al., 2014), it was assumed the creation of a more liquid product enabled easier LESSE (trailing hose) use (**Figure 5**).

Figure 5. Summary box describing bandspreading and the implications for ammonia emission reduction.

<p>Bandspreading/ Trailing Hose</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • One type of Low-Emission Slurry Spreading Equipment (LESSE) • Discharges slurry material at or just above ground level through a series of hanging or trailing pipes or hoses which hang a short distance above the soil or are dragged along the soil surface. • An effective way to increase the amount of nutrient available for crop growth from slurry application, while reducing loss of nutrients
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Four scenarios of trailing hose use were modelled as part of a sensitivity analysis (**Table 4**). The percentages represent the proportion of farms using trailing hose application, comparing the conventional baseline (raw slurry) with the F2E supply chain (liquid slurry following separation).

- The impact of introducing the F2E supply chain on ammonia emissions was interpreted as the difference between emissions from conventional practices (the conventional baseline scenario) and those of a farm operating within the F2E supply chain (with a separation step and slurry solids export).

Table 4. Proportion of farms (%) using trailing hose application under conventional (raw slurry) and F2E (separated slurry) systems across four scenarios. Abbreviations: LESSE, low emission slurry spreading equipment.

Scenario	Proportion of farms using trailing hose as compared with surface spreading	
	Conventional baseline (no separation of slurry)	F2E supply chain (separation of slurry)
Scenario 1	0%	100%
Scenario 2	50%	75%
Scenario 3	50%	100%
Scenario 4	100%	100%

The full set of assumptions used for a farm within the F2E supply chain are summarised in **Table 5**.

Table 5. Assumptions for ammonia emissions from each farm stage operating within the F2E supply chain. Abbreviations: EF, Emission factor; BHE, BH-Estates; N, nitrogen; TAN, total ammoniacal nitrogen.

Emission source	Assumptions
Animal housing	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • 100 dairy cow equivalents per farm • 118 kg N excreted per cow per year (public consultation on the proposed Nutrients Action Programme 2026-2029) • 47% of excreted N assumed to be TAN (BHE Dataset*) • Fully enclosed system: animals housed year-round (365 days) on a slurry-based system • Housing ammonia EF^{**}: 27.7% of excreted TAN (Misselbrook et al., 2023).
Storage (Pre and post separation)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • 100% raw slurry stored underground (EF 5%) (Misselbrook et al., 2023) • 100% Liquid fraction (post-separation) stored above ground with assumed crust formation (EF 5%)
Separation	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Screw-press separation partitions 5.8% of TAN into the solid fraction (BHE Dataset*)
Application to land	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Four scenarios were created for application ammonia emissions, representing the proportion of conventional farms versus farms that have undergone separation, using trailing hose as specified in Table 4 • Spreading EF for ammonia at 37.25% of applied slurry TAN for splash plate application (Misselbrook et al., 2023) • 30% reduction in ammonia emissions due to use of trailing hose (Bittman et al, 2014; Misselbrook et al., 2023) • An 18% reduction in ammonia emissions due to increased infiltration through dry matter reduction (Misselbrook et al., 2023; Bittman et al., 2014)

*BHE (BH-Estates) dataset refers to a nutrient and physical property dataset of biomass samples created within the F2E project

** Emission factor (EF) = % of $\text{NH}_3\text{-N}$ (TAN) lost as NH_3 (ammonia).

3.3.2 Assumptions for anaerobic digester plants in the F2E supply chain

At the AD site, ammonia emissions were estimated from feedstock storage, as well as from the storage and application of digestate/liquid digestate. To quantify the ammonia emissions from an AD plant within the F2E supply chain, the following assumptions were made.

- Within the F2E supply chain, the AD plant differ from the conventional baseline through the inclusion of slurry solids as feedstock. To evaluate the effect of feedstock composition on ammonia emissions, three scenarios were modelled in which slurry solids comprised 50%, 75% and 100% of the AD feedstock, with the remaining proportion assumed to be grass silage.
- Mechanical separation of digestate using decanting centrifuge technology is assumed at each AD plant within the F2E supply chain. This produces a solid digestate fraction that is exported (with no associated AD plant emissions) and a liquid digestate fraction that is applied to land, replacing raw unprocessed digestate. The lower dry matter content of the liquid digestate compared with raw digestate reduces ammonia emissions during land application due to increased infiltration (Bittman et al., 2014).
- As AD plants in Northern Ireland are required to use LESSE for the application of digestate, 100% LESSE use was assumed in both the conventional baseline and within the F2E supply chain at the AD plant.

Ammonia emissions for the AD plant within the F2E supply chain were calculated and compared with the conventional AD baseline, to assess the impact of the F2E supply chain on ammonia emissions. Full assumptions used for calculating AD plant ammonia emissions are summarised in **Table 6**.

Table 6. Assumptions for ammonia emissions at an anaerobic digester (AD) plant, with references where available. Abbreviations: N, nitrogen; TAN, total ammoniacal nitrogen; AD, anaerobic digestion.

Parameter	Assumption/Source			Units
Loss from feedstock storage				
Feedstock tonnage (fresh mass) per AD plant	13,000	14,000	15,000	tonnes yr ⁻¹
Proportion of feedstock as slurry solids	50	75	100	%
Feeder farms per AD plant	47	68	97	No. of farms
TAN content of slurry solids	1.33*			kg tonne ⁻¹ (fresh mass)
TAN content of grass silage	1.7*			kg tonne ⁻¹ (fresh mass)
Emission factor from slurry solids storage (uncovered storage)	26 (Misselbrook et al., 2023)			% of TAN
Emission factor from grass silage storage	4 (GP feeds, n.d.)			% of TAN
Loss from digestate storage				
Digestate produced	90			% of feedstock
TAN:N ratio	39 (silage)*			%
Proportion of organic N mineralised to TAN through digestion	31 (slurry solids)*			%
Above ground storage	70 (DAERA, Horizon Scanning Report)			%
Emission factor for above ground digestate storage	100			% of the year
Emission factor for above ground liquid digestate storage	10 (Misselbrook et al., 2023)			% of TAN in store
Emission reduction due to covering store	10 (Misselbrook et al., 2023)			% of TAN in store
Proportion of above ground stores covered	80 (Misselbrook et al., 2023)			%
Proportion of above ground stores covered	100			%
Separation of solid and liquid digestate				
Type of separation	Decanting centrifuge			N/A
TAN partitioned to solid fraction	20*			% of input TAN

Table 6 (cont.) Assumptions for ammonia emissions at anaerobic digester (AD) plant, with references where available. Abbreviations: TAN, total ammoniacal nitrogen.

Parameter	Assumption/Source	Units
Proportion of digestate solids exported	100	%
Loss from liquid digestate storage		
Emission factor	10 (Misselbrook et al., 2023)	% of TAN in store
Emission reduction due to covering store	80	%
Loss from application to land		
Emission factor from broadcast application	37 (Misselbrook et al., 2023)	% of TAN applied to land
Emission reduction due to use of trailing hose	30	%
Emission reduction due to increased infiltration	18 (Misselbrook et al., 2023; Bittman et al., 2014)	%

*BHE dataset refers to a nutrient and physical property dataset of biomass samples created within the F2E project.

3.3.3 Ammonia emissions from dryer facilities in the F2E supply chain

At the drying facility, ammonia loss was calculated from two main sources:

1. storage of solid digestate, and
2. the drying process.

It is assumed that both the input loading of solid digestate and the entire drying process occur within a building fitted with an acid-based ammonia scrubber, reducing ammonia emissions by 95% compared to unmitigated emissions (Moore et al., 2019).

The drying site is assumed to receive solid digestate from AD plants, with three AD plants supplying one drying site. An EF of 26.3% of available TAN is applied to biomass storage, consistent with emission levels from uncovered manure heaps (Misselbrook et al., 2023). During drying, 80% of the TAN is assumed to be emitted as ammonia if not abated by the ammonia scrubber, which recovers nitrogen (Awiszus et al., 2018).

From the dryer facilities, ammonium sulphate $(\text{NH}_4)_2\text{SO}_4$ is produced by the scrubbing process, which is used in the case study to replace urea fertiliser to satisfy crop nitrogen demands. Differing from the final BBF, $(\text{NH}_4)_2\text{SO}_4$ is assumed to be used within Northern Ireland, replacing urea with recycled nitrogen, leading to associated ammonia emission reductions.

Full assumptions used for calculating ammonia emission reductions from displacing urea with ammonium sulphate captured from the scrubbing process at the drying facility are summarised in **Table 7**.

Table 7. Assumptions for calculating ammonia emission reductions from displacing urea with ammonium sulphate captured from the scrubbing process at the drying facility. Abbreviations: N, nitrogen; TAN, total ammoniacal nitrogen; $(\text{NH}_4)_2\text{SO}_4$, ammonium sulphate.

Scenario	Assumption	Source
Scrubber efficiency for removal of NH_3 from air	95%	Moore et al., 2019
Conversion of NH_3 to $(\text{NH}_4)_2\text{SO}_4$	Multiply by 3.9	Molecular weight
Proportion of $(\text{NH}_4)_2\text{SO}_4$ captured via scrubbing assumed to displace urea use	25%	Model assumption
Tonnes of urea displaced per dryer	8-10	Model assumption
Nitrogen mass share of $(\text{NH}_4)_2\text{SO}_4$	21.2%	Yara
Nitrogen mass share of urea	46%	Yara
Emission factor for applying $(\text{NH}_4)_2\text{SO}_4$ to land (surface application)	6%	Yara
Emission factor for applying urea to land (surface application)	13.1%	Yara

Photo: A tractor lifts a heap of digestate solids after mechanical separation. Proper handling of these nutrient-rich solids helps recycle nitrogen and phosphorus on farms, supporting sustainable fertilisation while reducing environmental losses.

Results: ammonia emissions in the Farm2Export supply chain

4.1 Ammonia emissions from livestock farms in the F2E supply chain

At the farm scale, adoption of the F2E system, that is, the separation of slurry followed by the export of slurry solids, resulted in a net decrease in the emission of ammonia by between 239-750 kg NH₃ yr⁻¹ farm⁻¹, depending on the proportion of farms that transitioned from splash plate to trailing hose for land spreading.

As shown in **Table 8**, ammonia emissions from animal housing remain unchanged, storage emissions increased while application emissions decreased when comparing a conventional baseline farm with a farm within the F2E supply chain. **Figure 6** further illustrates the impact of the F2E supply chain on farm ammonia emissions and total ammonia savings for each process and application scenario.

Table 8. Ammonia emissions (kg NH₃ yr⁻¹) from animal housing, slurry storage and application for conventional and F2E farm systems. Net changes in ammonia emissions resulting from the implementation of the F2E system at the farm scale, along with percentage change, are also presented. Abbreviations: LESSE, Low Emission Slurry Spreading Equipment; NH₃, ammonia.

Application scenario (See Table 4)		S1	S2	S3	S4
		100-100% LESSE use	50-75% LESSE use	50-100% LESSE use	0-100% LESSE use
Process		Ammonia emissions (kg NH ₃ yr ⁻¹)			
Housing	Conventional baseline	1,868	1,868	1,868	1,868
	F2E	1,868	1,868	1,868	1,868
Storage	Conventional baseline	244	244	244	244
	F2E	391	391	391	391
Application	Conventional baseline	1,194	1,450	1,450	1,706
	F2E	808	925	808	808
Net ammonia emissions reduction at farm scale*		-239	-378	-495	-750
Net % change in ammonia emissions at farm scale		-7%	-11%	-14%	-20%

*Negative numbers indicate decreased ammonia emissions.

Figure 6. Impact of the F2E supply chain on livestock farm ammonia emissions ($\text{kg NH}_3 \text{ yr}^{-1}$) across four LESSE use scenarios. Negative numbers indicate decreased emissions and positive numbers indicate increased emissions in the scenarios. Abbreviations: LESSE, Low Emission Slurry Spreading Equipment; NH_3 , ammonia.

Within the F2E supply chain, ammonia emissions from slurry storage, including the separated liquid fraction, increased by 60% relative to the conventional baseline of raw slurry storage. This was partly due to the higher concentration of TAN in the liquid slurry fraction compared with non-separated slurry.

Ammonia emissions from slurry application decreased for the farm within the F2E supply chain for each LESSE use scenario. Assuming 50% trailing hose use in the conventional baseline and 75% in the F2E system, application emissions decreased by 36%.

At the whole-farm scale, ammonia emissions are estimated to decrease by 378 $\text{kg NH}_3 \text{ farm}^{-1} \text{ yr}^{-1}$, assuming LESSE use increased from 50-75%, representing a net ammonia emission reduction of approximately 11%.

4.2 Ammonia emissions from anaerobic digester plant in the F2E supply chain

For the AD plant, the F2E system, i.e. the use of slurry solids as a feedstock for AD and the separation and export of digestate solids through a decanting centrifuge, resulted in a net decrease of 1,080–2,850 kg NH₃ yr⁻¹, depending on the proportion of slurry solids in the feedstock (50–100%) (Table 9). Figure 7 further illustrates the impact of the F2E supply chain on AD ammonia emissions and total ammonia emission reductions for each process and feedstock scenario.

Table 9. Ammonia emissions (kg NH₃ yr⁻¹) from the AD process stage for three scenarios, assuming 50%, 75%, and 100% slurry solids in the feedstock. Net changes in emissions are calculated as the difference between a conventional baseline AD plant and an AD plant within the F2E supply chain, and are presented in kg NH₃ yr⁻¹ and as a percentage change. Abbreviations: AD, anaerobic digestion; NH₃, ammonia.

Process		Conventional AD ammonia emissions (kg NH ₃ yr ⁻¹)	F2E AD ammonia emissions (kg NH ₃ yr ⁻¹)	Net change in ammonia emissions at AD plant (kg NH ₃ yr ⁻¹) / % diff.	
Feedstock storage	50% slurry solids feedstock	1,075	3,302	-2850	-17.9%
Digestate storage		1,081	1,595		
Application		13,749	8,158		
Feedstock storage	75% slurry solids feedstock	1,075	4,756	-1957	-12.3%
Digestate storage		1,081	1,503		
Application		13,749	7,690		
Feedstock storage	100% slurry solids feedstock	1,075	6,380	-1080	-6.8%
Digestate storage		1,081	1,381		
Application		13,749	7,065		

Figure 7. Impact of the F2E supply chain on AD facility ammonia emissions ($\text{kg NH}_3 \text{ yr}^{-1}$) across three slurry solid feedstock scenarios. Negative numbers indicate decreased emissions and positive numbers indicate increased emissions in the scenarios. Abbreviations: AD, anaerobic digestion; NH_3 , ammonia.

Within the F2E supply chain, ammonia emissions at the feedstock and digestate storage stage increased, reflecting the higher concentration of TAN in slurry solids compared with grass silage at the feedstock stage, and in liquid digestate compared with raw digestate post-separation. When 50%-100% of feedstock was displaced with slurry solids, ammonia emissions at the feedstock storage stage increased by 200–500%. However, as the proportion of slurry solids in the feedstock increased, emissions from digestate and liquid digestate storage decreased, as a greater portion of TAN had already been lost prior to the AD process.

Reductions in ammonia emissions were observed at the digestate application stage, with decreases of 48%, 39%, and 28% when 50%, 75%, and 100% of slurry solids were used as feedstock, respectively, compared with conventional application.

At the whole AD plant scale, ammonia emissions are estimated to decrease by 1,957 $\text{kg NH}_3 \text{ yr}^{-1} \text{ AD}^{-1}$ assuming slurry solids constituted 75% of the feedstock. This corresponds to an overall 12.3% reduction in emissions for each AD plant.

4.3 Ammonia emissions from drying facilities in the F2E supply chain

At the dryer facility there was an overall increase in ammonia emissions of 919–1,061 kg NH₃ yr⁻¹ dryer⁻¹, depending on the feedstock slurry solid proportions utilised by the AD (50–100%).

This increase is primarily due to ammonia emissions from digestate storage and drying, which occur in the F2E supply chain but are absent in the conventional baseline scenario. Ammonia emissions decrease slightly due to the displacement of urea fertiliser with ammonium sulphate recovered from the acid scrubbing process, resulting in a reduction of 50–60 kg NH₃ yr⁻¹ dryer⁻¹. However, when considering the entire drying process, the net effect is still an overall increase in emissions. **Figure 8** further illustrates the impact of the F2E supply chain on dryer ammonia emissions and total ammonia savings for each process and feedstock scenario.

Figure 8. Impact of the F2E supply chain on ammonia emissions (kg NH₃ yr⁻¹) from a drying facility processing three slurry solid feedstock proportions. Negative numbers indicate decreased emissions and positive numbers indicate increased emissions in the scenarios. Abbreviations: AD, anaerobic digester, NH₃, ammonia.

4.4 Ammonia emissions across the full F2E supply chain

Table 10 presents the overall impact of the F2E supply chain system on ammonia emissions for the full modelled system, comprising 950-1,900 farms, 20-23 AD plants, and 7 dryers supplying one BBF plant, as detailed in **Table 2**. **Figure 9** presents the whole supply chain ammonia emission savings in graphical form, assuming slurry solids represent 75% of AD feedstock (1430 farms, 21 AD facilities and 7 dryers), across four LESSE use scenarios.

Figure 9. Impact of the F2E supply chain on ammonia emissions ($\text{kg NH}_3 \text{ yr}^{-1}$) across the whole supply chain: 1430 farms, 21 AD facilities and 7 dryers, across four LESSE use scenarios. Negative numbers indicate decreased emissions and positive numbers indicate increased emissions in the scenarios. Abbreviations: AD, anaerobic digester; LESSE, Low Emission Slurry Spreading Equipment.

Table 10. Impact of the proposed F2E supply chain on ammonia emissions ($\text{kg NH}_3 \text{ yr}^{-1}$) in Northern Ireland, assuming (a) 25% LESSE use and (b) a 75:25 slurry solids:silage feedstock ratio. Abbreviations: AD, anaerobic digester; BFF, bio-based fertiliser; NH_3 , ammonia, LESSE, Low Emission Slurry Spreading Equipment.

Scenario	System description		Ammonia emissions within the F2E supply chain ($\text{kg NH}_3 \text{ yr}^{-1}$)			Net ammonia saving ($\text{kg NH}_3 \text{ yr}^{-1}$)	% of ammonia reduction target
	LESSE	% Feedstock as slurry solids	Farm emissions	AD emissions	Dryer emissions		
1		50% of AD feedstock as slurry solids	-227,159	-64,251	+7,257	284,153	6
2	100%-100% LESSE (No LESSE impact)	75% of AD feedstock as slurry solids	-340,739	-40,966	+6,841	374,864	8
3		100% of AD feedstock as slurry solids	-454,318	-21,095	+6,284	469,129	10
4		50% of AD feedstock as slurry solids	-359,748	-64,251	+7,257	416,742	9
5	50%-75% LESSE use on the farm	75% of AD feedstock as slurry solids	-539,622	-40,966	+6,841	573,748	12
6		100% of AD feedstock as slurry solids	-719,497	-21,095	+6,284	734,307	16
7		50% of AD feedstock as slurry solids	-470,732	-64,251	+7,257	527,726	11
8	50%-100% LESSE use on the farm	75% of AD feedstock as slurry solids	-706,098	-40,966	+6,841	740,224	16
9		100% of AD feedstock as slurry solids	-941,465	-21,095	+6,284	956,275	21
10		50% of AD feedstock as slurry solids	-714,306	-64,251	+7,257	771,299	17
11	0%-100% LESSE use on the farm	75% of AD feedstock as slurry solids	-1,071,458	-40,966	+6,841	1,105,584	24
12		100% of AD feedstock as slurry solids	-1,428,611	-21,095	+6,284	1,443,422	31

*16% of 2005 ammonia levels by 2030, in line with the National Emission Ceilings Regulations (2018).

Scenario 5 in **Table 10** (i.e. row highlighted green) is also summarised in **Table 11**, and represents the supply chain scenario considered most reflective of the potential new system.

This scenario assumes that:

- 1,430 farms supply 21 AD plants with slurry solids,
- farm-level separation enables LESSE (trailing hose) use on 25% of farms, and
- slurry solids constitute 75% of the AD feedstock.

Total ammonia emissions across the entire supply chain are estimated to decrease by 11% relative to the conventional baseline. This reduction corresponds to 12% of Northern Ireland's agricultural ammonia reduction target, which is set at 16% (4.6 kt NH₃ N) of the 2005 baseline of 28.77 kt by 2030, in accordance with the National Emission Ceilings Regulations (2018).

Table 11. Impact of the proposed F2E supply chain on ammonia emissions (kg NH₃-N yr⁻¹) in Northern Ireland, assuming (a) 25% LESSE use and (b) a 75:25 slurry solids:silage feedstock ratio. Net ammonia reductions at each stage in the F2E supply chain in comparison to conventional cattle farm system shown in the green row. Abbreviations: NH₃, ammonia; AD, anaerobic digester; BFF, bio-based fertiliser.

Scenario	Livestock farm	AD plant	Dryer facilities	BBF plant	Total
Quantity	1,430 farms	21 AD plants	7 Dryer facilities	1 BBF plant	N/A
Conventional cattle farm system ammonia emissions (kg NH ₃ -N yr ⁻¹)	5,085,873	332,921	0	0	5,418,795
F2E supply chain ammonia emissions (kg NH ₃ -N yr ⁻¹)	4,546,251	291,956	6,841	0	4,845,047
Ammonia emission reductions (kg NH ₃ -N yr ⁻¹)	539,622	40,966	+6,841*	N/A**	573,748 equiv. (11%)

*Net increase in emissions from the dryer facilities

**No emission impact associated with BBF, as emissions deemed insignificant, however work is ongoing

5

Photo: A field of wheat. Crops like wheat benefit from bio-based fertilisers produced from recycled nutrients. Using these materials is a key part of transitioning to a circular nutrient system, supporting both environmental sustainability and national food security.

Discussion and conclusion

5.1 Overview of nitrogen management related to land-use and landscapes

In Northern Ireland, intensive livestock production continues to exert pressure on air and water quality, driven by surpluses of reactive nitrogen and phosphorus in many rural catchments. These surpluses have contributed to ecological degradation in sensitive habitats, rivers and lakes, including well-documented declines in Lough Neagh. Addressing these dual nutrient challenges requires an integrated approach that manages nitrogen and phosphorus together across the full agri-environmental system, rather than in isolation.

5.2 Benefits of the F2E approach

The Farm2Export (F2E) nutrient supply chain aims to reduce the pressure of livestock farming on the environment for Northern Ireland. By combining nutrient recovery and biomass processing from behind the farmgate, through anaerobic digestion, to the production of bio-based fertiliser (BBF) for managed nutrient redistribution. Farm2Export redirects nutrients away from sensitive parts of the landscape. This reduces nutrient loading at both the farm and anaerobic digester (AD) plant level, lessening agriculture's impact on water and air quality. Diffuse losses are driven more by soil drainage and hydrological connectivity than by livestock density, especially for phosphorus (Mellander et al., 2015), with small critical source areas (CSAs) responsible for disproportionate losses (Doody et al., 2012). National modelling using the Source Load Apportionment Model (SLAM) (Mockler, 2017) reinforces the need for targeted, site-specific interventions. F2E aligns with this evidence by removing nutrient-rich solids from CSAs and redistributing them to nutrient-deficient regions, thereby reducing run-off risk.

In parallel, the F2E system contributes to sustainable nutrient circularity and rural economic development by producing transportable, low-emission BBF that can displace synthetic fertilisers, and reduce nutrient losses and greenhouse gas emissions. Results from this report show that ammonium sulphate $(\text{NH}_4)_2\text{SO}_4$ recovered from 7 dryers could conservatively displace around 65 tonnes of existing urea fertiliser, which has significant benefits for ammonia reduction, carbon dioxide reduction and nutrient neutrality. This is viewed as a conservative displacement level as only 25% of the $(\text{NH}_4)_2\text{SO}_4$ captured was assumed to displace urea fertiliser, when in reality this could be higher. The final BBF produced from the dried digestate (post dryer) was not assumed to displace any nitrogen fertiliser in Northern Ireland, therefore no associated displacement savings were calculated. This also increases the conservative nature of the ammonia savings, as in reality there could be chemical nitrogen fertiliser displacement as a result of production and use of BBF in Northern Ireland. These co-benefits create opportunities for new business models in nutrient recovery, AD infrastructure, and low-carbon fertiliser supply chains.

The modelling in this study has quantified F2E's implications for air quality, estimating an 11% reduction in ammonia emissions compared with conventional business-as-usual management practices, assuming:

- 25% LESSE use on farms and
- a 75:25 slurry solids-to-silage feedstock ratio.

This reduction corresponds to 12% of the ammonia emission reduction required from Northern Ireland agriculture to meet its share of the UK's 2030 commitment under the National Emissions Ceiling Regulations (2018), equivalent to a reduction of 4,600 tonnes in agricultural ammonia emissions relative to 2005 levels (DAERA, 2025).

This modelling output, summarised fully in **Table 11**, is further considered conservative as greater adoption of LESSE, or more impactful forms of LESSE such as a trailing shoe, could be expected at the farm level, enabled by separation, which would improve nutrient use efficiency, reduce mineral nitrogen fertiliser use and lower nutrient losses.

These results are significant in the context of atmospheric ammonia concentrations in Northern Ireland, where 97% of these emissions are agricultural in origin and many designated sites already exceed ecological nitrogen thresholds (Gladkova, 2020; Brennan et al., 2020). Centralised manure treatment through F2E supply chain can reduce this burden, providing stability, transportability and redistribution of recovered nutrients.

Nutrient recovery is central to the F2E, but the deployment of nutrient recovery technologies is constrained by the Operational Protocol in Northern Ireland. This protocol, which governs planning, licensing and permitting, evaluates development-level ammonia emissions relative to habitat critical levels and loads. While this approach is effective for local impact assessment, it can limit recognition of wider system-level benefits, particularly when cumulative or distributed ammonia reductions across the supply chain cannot be readily quantified.

For example, processes such as drying generate point-source ammonia emissions, yet the broader benefits of the F2E supply chain, including emission reductions at farm and AD sites and the displacement of chemical nitrogen fertilisers, are difficult to account for within the planning framework. Although the supply chain represents a novel system for Northern Ireland, assessing the net ammonia impact of technologies across the entire supply chain remains constrained by current assessment procedures.

5.3 Spatial interactions

The trade-offs within the F2E supply chain, as summarised in the results section, show the importance of also considering spatial dimensions, including:

- Mitigation of background ammonia levels. An approach is required that recognises and accounts for the wider, system-scale benefits of measures that reduce ammonia emissions across Northern Ireland. This should include consideration of how such reductions influence baseline NH_3 concentrations at proposed development sites, balanced against the broader benefits delivered at multiple other locations that may not be subject to assessment at the same time.
- Further mitigation of process contribution at key sites. Consideration may be required for additional mitigation measures at specific development sites, particularly where these are located in proximity to designated nature protection areas. The approach outlined here provides a framework to quantify what additional measures may be necessary in such circumstances, ensuring that any localised increase in ammonia emissions does not occur in the context of, or offset, broader regional-scale reductions.

Such spatial aspects need further consideration, where specific case studies may be useful in illustrating the opportunities. This is especially relevant considering that for individual sites the exact conditions are likely to be unique. Nevertheless, a few detailed case studies can be useful to provide generic lessons, enabling a simplification of the assessment approach for subsequent cases. Such simplification may be essential when considering the engagement needed for the supply chain scale: 950-1900 farms, 20-23 AD systems and 7 dryers in Northern Ireland. Accordingly, 2-3 case studies, may enable a streamlining in assessing the remaining sites.

5.4 Regulatory gap

The present regulatory gap echoes the difficulties of previous strategies, where it has been suggested that these faltered due to high costs, planning delays and limited economic viability, particularly for smaller farms (Wright, 2023; Osborne-Sherlock, 2024). The fragmentation between environmental objectives and planning permissions can create a ‘delivery vacuum’ (i.e., a missing enabling approach), that leaves farmers under pressure to comply with regulations but without sufficient practical pathways to do so.

A regional, integrated supply chain such as the proposed F2E offers a way to bridge this gap. Its strength lies not only in individual technologies but in coordinating nutrient flows across space, from surplus to deficit zones, and across sectors, linking agriculture, energy and environment (water, air and soil quality). Nutrient management has too often been addressed through siloed nitrogen or phosphorus strategies (Cordell & Neset, 2014; Morseletto, 2019). By aligning both, the F2E approach provides a scalable model for sustainable nutrient management and could play a central role in enabling Northern Ireland’s transition to a more resilient agri-environmental system, if policy frameworks evolve to account for regional net benefits.

5.5 Conclusion

This study estimates that the F2E nutrient supply chain has the potential to deliver substantial reductions in ammonia emissions in Northern Ireland. Under the most feasible scenario, the overall net emission reduction relative to the conventional baseline is estimated at 11%, with a range of 8-19% across the scenarios modelled. This overall reduction comprises emission decreases of 11% at the farm level and 12% at the AD plant level, respectively.

These reductions are achieved through slurry separation, export of nutrient-rich solids and integration of slurry solids into AD. The feasible scenario assumed that 25% of farms in the supply chain transitioned from the use of a splash plate to a trailing hose for application (facilitated by separation and the production of a lower dry matter product) and that slurry solids comprised 75% of AD feedstock, meaning around 68 farms supplied solids to each AD plant.

When point-source emissions from the drying stage are combined with the emission savings achieved through displacement of chemical nitrogen fertiliser by captured ammonium sulphate $(\text{NH}_4)_2\text{SO}_4$, the drying stage results in a net increase of approximately 1,000 kg NH_3 yr^{-1} . Consideration of other scenarios could be used to show larger net reductions, including the displacement of chemical nitrogen fertiliser with the final BBF product within Northern Ireland and the adoption of more ambitious LESSE methods or uptake than assumed in this case study.

Beyond ammonia, F2E plays a critical role in rebalancing nutrient cycles, particularly phosphorus. By removing phosphorus-rich solids from CSAs and redistributing them to nutrient-deficient regions, the system can reduce run-off and help alleviate pressures on sensitive water bodies such as Lough Neagh, where high phosphorus loading is a persistent concern. This integrated approach demonstrates how system-scale nutrient management can simultaneously address air and water quality challenges. Additional environmental benefits may arise from nutrient export and redistribution, potential carbon capture and the production of enhanced-efficiency bio-based fertilisers at the BBF plant stage, which could further reduce reliance on synthetic fertilisers.

The study also highlights a regulatory gap for Northern Ireland: current site-level assessment frameworks struggle to capture system-wide benefits, effectively limiting where nutrient recovery and biomass processing facilities can be constructed under existing planning guidance and constraining their wider deployment.

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Appendix

Key Principles of Integrated Nutrient Management

Nutrient management has traditionally been approached in isolated sectors, focusing separately on individual nutrients such as nitrogen or phosphorus, or targeting distinct sources and impacts in isolation. However, this siloed approach fails to capture the complex and interconnected nature of nutrient flows across landscapes, water bodies, agricultural systems, and human activities. Nutrients do not exist or behave in isolation, nitrogen and phosphorus cycles overlap, sources interact, and environmental impacts cascade across spatial and temporal scales. Effective and sustainable nutrient management therefore requires an integrated framework that considers all nutrients, sources, pathways, and effects in a coordinated and holistic manner. Only by transcending traditional boundaries and fostering cross-sector collaboration can strategies be developed that simultaneously enhance agricultural productivity, protect water quality, and preserve ecosystem health.

In the following, we present 10 cross-cutting principles of integrated sustainable 'nutrient' management, based on a longer list of 24 principles for sustainable 'nitrogen' management in agriculture (Sutton et al., 2022) and 10 principles for sustainable nitrogen management across the anthropogenic nitrogen cycle (Brownlie et al., 2024).

Principle 1: Address all sources, forms, and movement of nutrients across space and time

Nutrients such as phosphorus and nitrogen enter and move through lake catchments and agricultural landscapes via multiple interconnected pathways. These include runoff from agricultural and urban areas, leaching into groundwater, erosion of nutrient-rich soils, atmospheric deposition, and discharges from wastewater systems. These flows are influenced by a complex interplay of factors such as land use, hydrology, climate variability, and human activities. Effective nutrient management requires a comprehensive and integrated approach that tracks and addresses all nutrient sources and forms at every stage of the anthropogenic nutrient cycle. This holistic understanding prevents localised interventions from simply shifting nutrient problems elsewhere, thereby reducing the risk of nutrient accumulation and eutrophication in vulnerable water bodies.

Principle 2: Reducing nutrient inputs is essential for controlling pollution

Limiting excessive nutrient inputs at the landscape level is fundamental to reducing nutrient losses downstream. This involves optimising fertiliser use through improved

nutrient management practices that match crop requirements without surplus application. By reducing inputs such as synthetic fertilisers and organic amendments to what crops need, nutrient use efficiency improves, losses to runoff and leaching decrease, and environmental impacts are minimised. Such reductions must be balanced carefully to maintain agricultural productivity and economic viability. Preventing nutrient pollution starts at its source and offers the greatest leverage for long-term water quality protection.

Principle 3: Reductions in nutrient losses must be matched by decreases in inputs or increases in outputs

Nutrient flows within landscapes are dynamic, and measures to reduce losses from one pathway can inadvertently increase nutrient availability elsewhere. For example, decreasing phosphorus runoff through reduced fertiliser application may lead to nutrient accumulation in soils or groundwater if not accompanied by increased nutrient uptake or removal. This principle emphasises the need for balance: total nutrient inputs to a system should align with outputs, including crop harvest, nutrient recovery, and losses, while accounting for storage changes in soils or sediments. Failure to maintain this balance risks perpetuating nutrient pollution problems despite localised management efforts.

Principle 4: Managing internal nutrient loading (e.g. from soils and lake sediments) is critical for aquatic ecosystem restoration

In lakes and water bodies with historical nutrient enrichment, phosphorus bound in sediments can be released back into the water column, sustaining eutrophication even when external nutrient inputs are reduced. Effective restoration therefore requires interventions that target this internal loading, including sediment oxygenation, chemical treatments such as alum application, sediment dredging, or biological controls. Addressing legacy nutrient stores is essential for achieving long-term improvements in water quality and aquatic ecosystem health, underscoring that external input controls alone may not be sufficient.

Principle 5: Transitioning to circular nutrient systems enhances sustainability

Sustainable nutrient management demands the recovery and recycling of nutrients from waste streams like manure and sewage sludge. Closing nutrient loops by returning recovered phosphorus and nitrogen to agricultural soils reduces reliance on finite mineral fertilisers and supports circular economy principles. This transition involves integrating livestock and crop systems more closely to facilitate nutrient reuse, adopting innovative technologies, and creating policy frameworks that incentivise nutrient recovery and reuse. Circular nutrient systems not only conserve resources but also reduce pollution risks, supporting resilient and sustainable food production.

Principle 6: Co-managing nitrogen and phosphorus maximises efficiency and benefits

Nitrogen and phosphorus share many sources, pathways, and environmental impacts, particularly in agricultural systems. Their combined presence contributes to multiple environmental pressures, including eutrophication, air pollution, and greenhouse gas emissions. Managing these nutrients together enables a more integrated and effective approach to reducing losses across environmental media. Strategies that simultaneously address nitrogen and phosphorus can generate synergistic benefits, improving nutrient use efficiency, supporting resource recovery, and minimising wider environmental and economic impacts, rather than treating each nutrient independently.

Principle 7: Site-specific management based on local conditions is essential

The vulnerability of land and water bodies to nutrient losses varies significantly depending on local factors such as soil type, land use, hydrological regime, and climate. As a result, nutrient management practices must be tailored to these conditions to be effective. Techniques such as precision agriculture, targeted buffer zones, and adaptive land management ensure that nutrient inputs and mitigation measures are optimally applied where they are most needed. Site-specific approaches maximise nutrient use efficiency and minimise environmental impacts, reflecting the diverse realities across catchments.

Principle 8: Cost-effective solutions and stakeholder involvement are critical for success

For nutrient management to be implemented widely and sustainably, it must be both affordable and practical for those responsible farmers, municipalities, wastewater operators, and other stakeholders. Socioeconomic barriers can impede adoption of improved practices, especially in agriculture, where financial constraints are common. Policy frameworks should therefore incorporate incentives, technical support, and accessible technologies to enable stakeholders to transition toward sustainable nutrient management. Engaging stakeholders through education, collaboration, and participatory decision-making fosters ownership and long-term commitment.

Principle 9: Shared responsibility across multiple sectors is necessary

Nutrient pollution is a complex issue that transcends individual sectors and jurisdictions. Effective management requires coordinated collaboration among policymakers, land managers, farmers, urban planners, water authorities, and communities. This multi-sectoral approach ensures that strategies address all sources and pathways of nutrient pollution comprehensively. Open communication and knowledge exchange between stakeholders support the development of scientifically sound, cost-effective, and socially acceptable solutions that can be implemented across scales.

Principle 10: Trade-offs must be considered when setting priorities

Balancing environmental protection with economic and social objectives is an inherent challenge in nutrient management. For example, while reducing fertiliser application improves water quality, it must not compromise food security or farm incomes. Similarly, costly lake restoration interventions need to be weighed against alternative strategies and long-term benefits. Effective nutrient management requires flexibility and careful prioritisation that considers multiple factors, including ecosystem health, economic viability, and social acceptance, to develop sustainable and resilient solutions.

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Farm2Export: Ammonia

At present, manure and nutrient management in Northern Ireland is often fragmented across farm and processing stages, limiting opportunities to reduce emissions and improve resource efficiency. Integrated approaches are needed to recover, redistribute, and reuse nutrients while supporting agricultural productivity.

This report assesses the Farm2Export supply chain, an integrated system combining on-farm slurry separation with anaerobic digestion and downstream processing to produce transportable bio-based fertilisers. Ammonia emissions are evaluated across the full supply chain under different management scenarios, including the use of low emission slurry spreading equipment and varying feedstock compositions. The results show that coordinated nutrient recovery can reduce emissions, rebalance regional nutrient surpluses, and support renewable energy generation. The findings highlight opportunities to improve nitrogen and phosphorus management through aligned policies, optimised digestate handling, and wider adoption of nutrient recovery technologies, supporting sustainable nutrient management, environmental protection, and long-term food security.

